

Certificate Verification (Special Round)

Acknowledgement No: 18485

Date :12-02-2021 14:59:10

Candidate Details			
HTNO	: 9114180314	Name	: M BHAGYA LAXMI
Father's Name	: M NARSIMHA REDDY	Marks in Qualifying Exam	: 7
Mother's Name	: M ARUNDHA	Max. Marks in Qualifying Exam	: 10
Gender	: F	Qualifying percentage of Marks	:
Date of Birth	: 02/03/1999	SSC Hall Ticket No.	: 1437144282
Mobile No	: 9398905410	Month & Year of Passing SSC	: 5-2014
Email ID	: bhagyareddy949@gmail.com	Parental Income	: Lower
Aadhar Card Number	: 550568079424	Qualifying Degree	: BPharm (BACHELOR OF PHARMACY)
Local Region	: OU	Specialization	: PHARMACY
Minority	: Non-Minority	Test Code	: PY
Caste Category	: OC		
Special Category	: ,,,		

Provisional Allotment Details	
Alloted College : CBCP1JHPHCETSREG - CHILKUR BALAJI COLLEGE OF PHARMACY RVS NAGAR, AZIZ NAGAR POST, MOINABAD ROAD, NEAR A.P.POLICE ACADEMY	Course : PHARMACEUTICS
College Type : AFF	Payment Type : REG
Under Alloted Category : REG_OPEN_OU_GEN	Allotedin : Spl Round

Verified the following original certificates::		
SNo.	Name of the Certificate	Status
1	Entrance Test Score Card	Y
2	Memorandum of marks of SSC or equivalent	Y
3	Memorandum of marks in Qualifying Examination	Y
4	Provisional Certificate of Qualifying Examination	Y
5	Study certificates from 10th class to Graduation	Y
6	Integrated Community Certificate (Caste Certificate)	NA
7	Transfer Certificate	Y
8	Income Certificate issued after 01/01/2020	Y
9	Minority Certificate	NA
10	NCC / CAP / PH / Sports Certificate	NA

Note:: Y-Original Verified N-No Certificate NA-Not applicable

Signature of Candidate

Signature of Principal
With office seal

Provisional Allotment Order (Special Round)

Acknowledgement No: 18485

Date :12-02-2021 14:59:10

Candidate Details			
HT.No	: 9114180314	Rank	: 2875
Name	: M BHAGYA LAXMI	Gender	: F
Father's Name	: M NARSIMHA REDDY	Date of Birth	: 02-03-1999
Parental Income	: Lower	Mobile No.	: 9398905410
Category	: OC	Region	: OU
SpecialCategory	: ,,,	Minority	: Non-Minority

Provisional Allotment Details			
Alloted College	: CBCP1JHPHCETSREG - CHILKUR BALAJI COLLEGE OF PHARMACY RVS NAGAR, AZIZ NAGAR POST, MOINABAD ROAD, NEAR A.P.POLICE ACADEMY	Course	: PHARMACEUTICS
College Type	: AFF	Payment Type	: REG
Under Alloted Category	: REG_OPEN_OU_GEN	Allotedin	: Spl Round

Course Fee Rs	: 55000.00 /-
Amount paid in 1st phase Rs	: .00 /-
Fee paid Rs	: .00 /-

Instructions to candidates

1. In case the candidate wishes to cancel their admission, they are required to approach the Principal of the college concerned only with a request letter.
2. If the candidate cancels his/her admission, tuition fee will be refunded as following:
 - a. After first phase full tuition fee will be refunded.
 - b. 50% of the amount will be refunded after final phase.
3. **Class work commenced from 21th Dec.,2020.**
4. The students claim for Reimbursement of Tution Fee(RTF) will be considered subject to verification and eligibility criteria prescribed by Government of Telangana/Andra Pradesh from time to time. In the event of the candidate found not eligible for fee reimbursement the candidate shall have to pay the total fee.
5. Student who secured admission through **GATE/GPAT** are **not eligible for fee reimbursement**
6. Tuition fee fixed is Semester fee for M.Tech./M.Pharm. and Annual fee for Pharm-D.

Sd /-
CONVENER
TS PGEC / PGECET 2020